

Quantum Density $W^*(x)W(x)$ versus Classical Density constant/ $\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$

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It is well-known that one may create a classical probability $P(x)dx$ by equating it to the amount of time $dt(x)$ spend in each dx region. Given that $dx=v(x) dt(x)$, for constant dx units, one has: $P(x)dx= C dx/|v(x)|$. In quantum mechanics, averages are calculated using $P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x) dx$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. We consider $W(x)$ for the time-independent Schrodinger equation for convenience. The idea seems to be that using the correspondence principle, if energy levels approach infinite, averages calculated using the classical approach match those using the quantum mechanical equation.

In particular, in (1) the Hamiltonian $H= p^2/2m + mgx$ is considered, i.e. motion in a gravitational field. Probability densities are calculated classically and quantum mechanically. Airy functions appear in the quantum solution and using mathematical properties of these functions it is shown in (1) that for high energy levels $\langle x \rangle$ is the same both classically and quantum mechanically.

Here we wish to investigate why $W(x)W(x) dx = Cdx/|v(x)|$ in the high energy limit. In quantum mechanics, one does not have fixed lengths, rather a length unit is defined by \hbar/p . For a bound quantum system, the base length of crests and troughs (a kind of varying half wavelength) may be large with respect to the system length. As the energy level increases, the base lengths of the crests and troughs become tiny, but they are still variable. We suggest that they are given by \hbar/p where one may estimate p through $|dW/dx / W|$. In other words, even in the high energy limit, the quantum picture is one in which dt , i.e. little time intervals, are defined through \hbar/E in $\exp(-iEt)$ where E is kinetic energy nonrelativistically. A time unit for a quantum free particle goes as $1/\text{kinetic energy} = 1/vv = dt = P(x) dx$ where $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $dx=\hbar/(mv)$. Thus, $W(x)W(x)$ must go as $1/|v(x)|$ we suggest. Our argument is nonrelativistic.

Classical and Quantum Probabilities

Classically, one may define $P(x)dx$ as equivalent to the amount of time an object spends in dx , where dx is a constant. Thus:

$$dx = v(x) dt(x) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{This yields: } P(x)dx= C/|v(x)| = C / \sqrt{(E- V(x) (2m))} \quad ((2))$$

For the Newtonian case of motion in a gravitational field (1):

$$P(x) = 1/ \{2H \sqrt{H-x}\} \quad ((3))$$

Here we use x for what would usually be called the y axis for convenience.

One may then calculate the average: $\langle x \rangle = \text{Integral } x P(x) dx$ or

{ $1/\sqrt{2}$ \sqrt{H} } $\int_0^H x dx / \sqrt{H-y}$ let $y= H \sin^2(\theta)$ and use

the result (2) for $\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^2(\theta) \sin^2(\theta) d\theta$ ($2/\sqrt{H}$) }

to find that: $\langle x \rangle = \frac{2}{3} H$ ((4)).

Quantum mechanically, one solves the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + mgx W = E W \quad ((5))$$

The solution is an Airy function. (For details see (1)).

As a result, one must deal with asymptotic forms for high energy levels and mathematical identities in order to calculate $\langle x \rangle$ in the high energy limit.

This procedure has been carried out in (1) and the result is: $\langle x \rangle = \frac{2}{3} \langle H_n \rangle$ where H_n tends to H in the high n limit. In other words, one obtains the classical result.

Here, we want to consider a general reason why $W^*(x)W(x)$ should tend to $C/|v|$. Such a relationship guarantees the results of (1).

Linking Quantum and Classical Probabilities

Quantum mechanical probability is given by: $P(x)dx = W^*(x)W(x)dx$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction for a bound state. In general $W(x)=\sum_n a_n W_n(x)$ where n denotes the energy level. Given that $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ involves periodic functions, one expects solutions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation to be periodic with different crest/trough heights and base widths.

In quantum mechanics, the notion of momentum as mv (nonrelativistically) does not disappear. Neither does the notion of velocity, because given $\exp(ipx)$ and rest mass m_0 , the momentum is p and the velocity p/m and these are both experimentally measurable. In creating a wavefunction, $W(x)=\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, one deals with averages of sharp p values with the probabilities $\exp(ipx)$. The particle is no longer localized, but is loosely localized in crests and troughs, with the looseness being tied to the base length of the crest/trough. As energy levels increase, the particle becomes more and more localized because the base lengths of the crests/troughs become tiny. If a particle is in a tiny dx region because a crest fits in dx , then average kinetic energy in that region which is always equal to $.5 m v(x)v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity seems to take on a physical sense with v_{rms} from $KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = .5 m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$ no longer applying to an average.

One may note that for any energy level:

$$KE(ave) = KE_{classical} = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \quad ((6))$$

If a crest is very sharp and exists within a dx , one may find an average momentum for the rising part of the crest. This should be associated with an average length through:

$$dx_1 = \hbar / \langle p_{ave} \rangle \quad ((7))$$

Dx_1 should be very small. In such a case, one may consider:

$$W(x)W(x) (-1/2m) d/dx dW/dx / W dx_1 = W(x)W(x) v(x)v(x).5m \ 1/p \quad ((8))$$

Here $v(x)$ is classical velocity, but it should be essentially equal to p/m (nonrelativistically).

In classical mechanics, one usually considers dx to be fixed, so the time spent in dx is the probability, i.e. $.5mv \ dt(x) = dx \ .5 \ mv \ Cdx/|v(x)|$.

If the average wavelength corresponds to tiny dx regions, then this approximates a free particle type of situation in which the same average amount of energy is contained in each wavelength, i.e.

$$\text{Constant} = P(x) \ 1/v \ (.5mv) = .5vv \ WW \ 1/v \ \rightarrow \ WW = C/|v| \quad ((9))$$

Alternatively, one may consider $P(x) \ 1/v$ to represent a time unit which goes as $1/\text{kinetic energy}$ (for a free particle) in quantum mechanics from $\exp(-iEt)$ form for $E=.5mv^2$ in the nonrelativistic case. This is like having a different free particle in each dx , with dx varying as it must be equal to \hbar/p .

Conclusion

In classical mechanics, one may consider a fixed dx length and define probability as the time spent in dx , i.e. $dt = dx/|v(x)| = P(x)dx$. In quantum mechanics, one does not have fixed lengths, rather a length unit is defined by \hbar/p . For a bound quantum system, the base length of crests and troughs (a kind of varying half wavelength) may be large with respect to the system length. As the energy level increases, the base lengths of the crests and troughs become tiny, but they are still variable. We suggest that they are given by \hbar/p where one may estimate p through $|dW/dx / W|$. In other words, even in the high energy limit, the quantum picture is one in which time units are defined through $\exp(-iEt)$ where E is kinetic energy nonrelativistically. In other words, one considers a free particle (i.e. it is moving in one direction).

A time unit goes as $1/\text{kinetic energy} = 1/v^2 = dt = P(x) \ dx$ where $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $dx=\hbar/(mv)$. Thus, $W(x)W(x)$ must go as $1/|v(x)|$ we suggest.

References

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